

Alternative Methods of Financing Higher Education in India: A Case Study of Central Sector Scholarship Scheme for College and University Students

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Abstract

One of the core ideas of higher education in the twenty-first century India is the transmission and transformation of India through education. The quality of higher education is considered to be an important factor in the national transformation process. Discussions on quality of higher education, very often, centre on institutional factors, teachers and infrastructure. The student which is the focus of educational process is very often forgotten as an important element influencing quality of higher education. Attracting meritorious students to higher education is a challenge. With the objective of attracting meritorious students, the Government of India introduced a scheme 'Central Sector Scholarship Scheme for College and University students'. This paper is based on an empirical study of 1,902 students availing this scholarship scheme from three States and one Union Territory in India. This paper attempts to analyse how far this scheme has succeeded in bringing meritorious students to higher education institutions. The conclusions drawn from the empirical evidences will be helpful in framing and improving student based financial support system to attract meritorious students to institutions of higher education.

Keywords Higher Education, India, Scholarship and Financing.

Introduction

India today has one of the most comprehensive higher education systems in the world. India has been a centre for learning from time immemorial. Modern-day India is one of the leading countries providing quality higher education to its citizens as well as to students and scholars from all over the world. Indian universities and institutes of higher education and research have made significant contributions to the transmission of knowledge and have played a leading role to transform the country into a modern industrialized and technologically advanced state. Education in India is not only comparable to the best institutions in the world but also available at a relatively affordable cost. <https://eoi.gov.in/eoisearch/MyPrint.php?1062?001/0011>.

In a developing country like India, socio-economic disparities at the inter and intra-state level are so severe that no single mechanism can be equally effective for addressing problems faced by the different states. Access to quality higher education is one of the important reasons for the existence of a skewed distribution among states.

The Central Sector Scheme of Scholarship for College and University Students is to provide opportunity to the meritorious students getting 80th percentile in the relevant stream from a particular board of examination in class XII of 10+2 pattern or equivalent and not belonging to the creamy layer. Moreover, this scheme is addressing the unique historical, political and economic characteristics of the country through implementation of reservation policy for SC, ST, OBC and physically challenged students. An opportunity is provided to the meritorious students coming from diverse background and culture and regions for continuing higher education. Through the introduction of affirmative action in the form of reservation policy, the issue of equity in higher education is addressed. Thus, the students of different categories / castes belonging to different regions get opportunity to continue higher education.

In addition, the scheme is meant for economically backward students whose parent's annual income is below 6 lakhs belonging to all categories. This scheme is also extending financial support to the students belonging to general category. In this respect, this scholarship scheme is unique as it provides chance to general category students also. It is also noteworthy that most of the schemes in India offer scholarship to weaker sections of the society and not to general category students.

Since these students are meritorious students so they qualify on the basis of marks of the qualifying examination. Since, these students are already meritorious so they perform better during their studies. The contribution of these meritorious students towards quality higher education is noteworthy. One important finding of the study is that these scholarship holders spend this scholarship amount (Rs.1000/- per month for 10 months in a year) for payment of the tuition fee, purchasing books and other study materials in order to continue their studies. Moreover, numerous scholarship holders are engaged in receiving professional/technical education from the reputed institutions.

Aim of study

1. To evaluate the performance of the 'Central Sector Scheme of Scholarship for College and University Students'
2. To understand the problems and issues of implementing the Scheme.
3. To assess the impact of the financial assistance provided to meritorious students who belong to socially and economically disadvantaged sections of the society.

Review of Literature

Lata Sharma (2023) As per the National Educational Policy-2020 emphasised the need of Gross Enrolment Ratio in Higher Education to be increased from 26.4% to 50% by 2030. About four crore students should be added in the education of higher studies. Its aim is to enhance the investment in the sector of education to 6% of GDP.

A wide variety of incentive programmes have been developed for those most in need, to help provide additional resources and to create adequate conditions for their schooling and academic success. Such programmes attempt in particular to compensate for both direct and indirect costs of schooling, by redirecting resources to geographical areas, schools or populations most in need, and by providing, for instance: additional funds to schools located in the poorest areas; scholarships or cash to pay for school costs or other household expenses; free food or transportation for children to encourage school attendance, etc. (Poisson, 2015). Another distinction in the concept of excellence is when we look at the system of higher education from within (*internal excellence*) and *excellence viewed as the fitness of the system to the society it serves*. This means that an institution may be judged to be internally excellent (i.e. attain the objectives it set out to achieve) yet be unfit in meeting the needs of the society. For example, in a country where managers and engineers are already in short supply and the system produces humanistic and theological scholars, the system will have a low score on the scale of excellence, no matter how excellent it's standard of scholarship. Similarly, a higher education system which produces only professional workers and no humanists will have the same problem. In a developing country, social demand for education is on the increase because of the instrumental value of higher education - its usefulness in getting suitable employment. In India, the share of scholarship is responded merely by 11 % (Sanyal, 1992). A key difference between PSS and any future RCUK initiative is that the former involved targeting of scholarship funding on the basis of socio-economic (and other) background characteristics in a circumstance where there were very few alternative public sources of finance. Studentships already exist for doctoral study and the key challenge is instead to ensure that the applicant pool is socio-economically diverse and that other potentially unfair barriers to progression are removed. The PSS programme analysis found that, apart from scholarships, several factors contributed to successful attempts to widen taught postgraduate participation. Successful PSS projects typically involved carefully planned 'inreach' and 'outreach' schemes to target graduates from groups underrepresented on taught postgraduate programmes. Where institutions were able to collaborate in this activity there appeared to be even greater success (Paul, 2016).

For the expansion of higher education in the country, government has consistently increased its share in the total expenditure on higher education, from 49.1 per cent in 1950-51 to more than 90 per cent in 1999 to finance the higher education. While, there is nominal fee for the students to pay to the institute that constitutes 10 to 15 per cent of the total budget of the institution (Maiti, 2001; Tilak, 1997). However, the fee contribution from the students to the institutions may vary significantly between central and a state institution which is a considerable amount to university income in the state universities. Many institutions (colleges & universities) offer fee waivers to women and scheduled caste and scheduled tribe students. The higher education financing system is beginning

to change and a policy of fostering financial independence in universities and degree colleges (reducing government allocations to universities and increasing user fees) has been in place since 1997. Despite policy pronouncements, action has been recently taken. While the UGC has the legal right to set tuition fees, it has not done so – in practice, it is the individual state governments and institutions that take the initiative.

Examining the different disparities, it is found that the important dimensions of the disparities are between social groups regarding their access to an enrolment in higher education. The share of scheduled castes to the total enrolment in higher education is 12.2 per cent while scheduled tribes account for 4.5 per cent during 2011-12 and 16.3 per cent during 2012-13. It is significant to note that the shares of SC enrolment in 2011-12 is higher than the national average in West Bengal (16.4%), Tripura (16.4%), Puducherry (15.9%) and Tamil Nadu (15.6%) (Varghese, 2015). The share of higher education expenditure in GDP was 0.86 in 2009-10 which further increased to 0.89 per cent in the year 2012-13. Due to these characters, the government and government funded institutions accounted major student enrolment share in this sector of education (Varghese, 2015:28).

The institution provides student support services reasonably necessary to enable each student to achieve the institution's goals for students. The support of students toward their educational goals usually requires a well-organized and appropriate program of student services, complemented by good staff leadership and broad-based institutional commitment. Within the scope of the institutional mission, student services can reinforce and extend the college's influence beyond the classroom. These services promote the comprehensive development of the student and they become an integral part of the educational process, helping to strengthen learning outcomes. Appropriate and comparable student services should support all students learning in the context of the institution's mission and chosen educational delivery system. Similarly, the institution should clearly convey to students their roles and responsibilities as partners in the educational process. The Government of India through Ministry of Education providing scholarship/incentive schemes to meritorious students belongs to socially and economically weaker section of the society. The central sector scheme of scholarship for college and university students is implementing since 2008.

Methodology

The study has been conducted with the objective to measure the student's awareness about the scheme, issues involved in the process of application and release of the incentive amount on time to the students and also its impact on meritorious students who belong to socially and economically disadvantaged sections of the society, including girls belonging to SC, ST, OBC and physically challenged communities in higher education. Also, to evaluate the performance of the 'Central Sector Scheme of Scholarship for College and University Students' by different Boards/States/UTs during the period from 2012-13 to 2016-17 and seek the utilisation pattern among different Boards/States/UTs in implementing the scholarship scheme.

A sample of 1,902 students (scholarship-holders) was taken from three states (Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Telangana) and one UT (Delhi) for the purpose of evaluation. The nodal officers, working in education boards, have been selected from each sample State/UT for the evaluation purpose.

This study is primarily based on primary data. To analyse issues related to the scheme, three different sets of questionnaires were developed for (i) Students availing the scholarship (ii) Heads of the colleges/universities/institutions (iii) CBSE/MHRD and nodal officers of the States/UTs.

Analysis

The scholarship under the scheme for its effective implementation is distributed among the States and UT's according to their population of 18-25 years of age-group. The distribution of the scholarship is further divided into three categories i.e. State Boards, Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) and Council for the Indian School Certificate Examinations (CICSE). Under the CBSE, the quota is reserved for Arunachal Pradesh, Delhi, Sikkim, Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Chandigarh, Dadra & Nagar Haveli, Daman & Diu and Lakshadweep. Before the division of Andhra Pradesh, the quota was 6097, but after the division, the State quota became 3527 and 2570 for Andhra Pradesh and Telangana respectively.

The share of the distributed quota of the scholarship among states is presented. Broadly, we can categorise this division into highly populated states and low populated States. The quota suggests that the maximum number of scholarships is allotted to Uttar Pradesh which constitutes approximately 14 per cent of the total scholarships, followed by Maharashtra (9 per cent), West Bengal (7.25 per cent), Bihar (6.86 per cent), Tamil Nadu (5.95 per cent), Madhya Pradesh (5.24 per cent), Karnataka (5.17 per cent), Rajasthan

(4.85 per cent), Gujarat (4.81 per cent) and Andhra Pradesh (4.30 per cent) as these states fall under the highly populated States.

Further, States like Odisha, Assam, Telangana, etc. have the quota between 2 and 3.5 per cent of the total scholarships. These scholarships are provided through the State Education Board, while, 8.36 per cent of the scholarships are provided through CBSE and 0.70 per cent of the total scholarships are provided by the ICSE. These distributions of the scholarships are further divided into gender, streams and social categories.

The problem pertaining to non-utilisation of these scholarships has been discussed in the table 2 in which discussions have been made on fresh allotment of the scholarships. The low and no utilisation of the scholarships are serious issues of the scheme at the implementation level that needs to be rectified immediately in order to provide the benefits to the poor and meritorious students.

Utilisation Pattern of the Scholarships

The scholarship-holder's/student's questionnaire sought response on the socio-economic and educational status of the family members in addition to issues and challenges involved in getting the scholarship amount. The filled-in schedule was investigated, analysed and tabulated the profile of family members and background of the student, socio-economic condition, income, education, academic achievement and difficulties in getting the scholarship. Further, the study helped in understanding the introduction, implementation, usage of the incentive and the extent to which the children of the underprivileged section of the society got benefited.

The table no.1 shows the distribution and disbursement of the scholarships to the eligible applicants. One of the aims of the Scheme was to encourage more (double) applications in comparison to the quota available. But, this two-year trend shows that the applications received against the available quota are marginally high.

In the year 2015-16, approximately 96,450 applications were received to avail the benefits of the scholarship scheme; which is approximately 18 per cent more applications received from the allocated quota. Out of these received applications, 47,901 applicants were males and 48,549 females. Both the applying and receiving rate of scholarship is marginally higher for the females than the males. Hence, it can be observed from the table 1 that 2 per cent more girls applied for the scholarship in comparison to boys.

Table 1: Year-wise number of students applied and selected for the scholarships

(2015-16 and 2016-17)

Year	Number of students applied		Total number of students received scholarships	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
2016-17	41893	44055	13720 (45.38)	16514 (54.62)
2015-16	47901	48549	19225 (46.92)	21747 (53.80)

Source: Department of Higher Education, MHRD, Government. Of India, 2017

As compared to the applications received under the scheme, approximately 42 per cent of the applicants were eligible for receiving the scholarships. Those who were awarded the scholarships comprised 47 per cent males and approximately 53 per cent females. It showed that the female students were more eligible and interested in availing this scholarship.

Graph 1: Year-wise allocation of scholarships against the applications received

(2015-16 and 2016-17)

Source: Department of Higher Education, MHRD, Government. of India, 2017

Similarly, in the academic year 2016-17, there were 85948 applications received from the students - approximately 5 per cent excess applications than the quota allocated under the Scheme. Of these applicants, 41893 (49 per cent) were males and 44055 (51 per cent) females. In this year also, female candidates have applied more than their male counterpart. But, it is to be noted that approximately 10 per cent less applications were received than previous year. Further, in this year, just above 35 per cent of the applicants were eligible for the scholarships which are approximately 7 per cent less than previous year's allotted scholarships.

In both the years, it is revealed that the approval rates of these applications were very less. As mentioned earlier, the awarded scholarship in the academic year 2015-16 was approximately 42.5 per cent which further declined by more than 7 per cent in the academic year 2016-17.

The male-female difference can be observed in the Graph 1, which shows that in the year 2015-16, approximately 20 per cent of the males and 22.55 per cent females received scholarships. The gender gap was above 2.5 per cent. But this gap increased to 3.25 per cent which shows that the performance of the female applicants is better than males.

Inter-State Variations in Utilisation of the Scholarships

The utilisation pattern for the last four academic years of the scholarships is discussed in the table below. It has been shown in the table above that the quota allocated to the States was according to their population. The scheme which was started in the academic year 2008-09 did not get much momentum in the initial years.

Table 2: Year-wise and board-wise allocation of fresh scholarships (2012-13 to 2015-16)

Sl. No.	States/UT/Boards	Quota/Year	2012-13 (percentage)	2013-14 (percentage)	2014-15 (percentage)	2015-16 (percentage)
1	CBSE	6853	54.40	63.84	67.66	51.26
2	ICSE	577	0.17	0.35	Pending	1.39
3	Andhra Pradesh	6097	88.65	97.92	98.38	68.53
4	Assam	2002	23.48	51.05	58.09	13.89
5	Bihar	5624	2.35	3.49	1.23	Pending
6	Chhattisgarh	1387	37.35	67.34	34.82	83.49
7	Goa	113	58.41	86.73	81.42	5.31
8	Gujarat	3944	81.31	77.10	53.78	64.43
9	Haryana	1591	100.00	99.56	98.49	88.87
10	Himachal Pradesh	461	86.77	49.02	68.11	Not Applied
11	Jammu & Kashmir	768	97.14	96.74	46.22	42.71
12	Jharkhand	1878	0.27	11.87	9.27	Pending
13	Karnataka	4237	97.81	90.77	87.59	85.27
14	Kerala	2324	100.00	99.35	99.23	61.53
15	Maharashtra	7417	39.11	36.25	85.78	58.11
16	Madhya Pradesh	4299	64.48	91.81	98.91	81.74
17	Manipur	181	6.63	100.00	87.29	16.57
18	Meghalaya	166	19.88	29.52	34.94	Not Applied
19	Mizoram	75	5.33	Pending	Pending	Not Applied
20	Nagaland	176	62.50	68.75	85.23	Pending
21	Odisha	2736	64.95	84.90	25.26	13.52
22	Punjab	1902	68.56	95.58	93.64	65.98
23	Rajasthan	3978	100.00	99.92	96.30	87.58
24	Tamil Nadu	4883	38.56	100.00	97.19	35.24
25	Telangana	2570	-	-	100.00	76.61
26	Tripura	236	100.00	100.00	96.19	47.46
27	Uttar Pradesh	11460	23.46	40.29	67.15	48.82
28	Uttarakhand	616	72.08	98.05	66.72	56.01
29	West Bengal	5941	46.32	57.82	7.61	26.22
30	Puducherry	78	100.00	100.00	100.00	Not Applied
Total		82000	53.30	65.28	65.76	49.96

Department of Higher Education, MHRD, Government of India, 2017

Even after four years of its implementation, the scholarships could not be offered to more than fifty per cent of the students. In the year 2012-13, merely 53.30 per cent of the fresh scholarships were allotted to the students. Similarly, in the subsequent years, this allotment increased more than 11 per cent. But, in the year 2014-15, this allotment was almost same as compared to the previous year. In the year 2015-16, it was further reduced to 50 per cent as compared to the previous year (60 per cent).

In the state-wise categorisation, it can be observed that very few states were able to implement the scheme in a better way. States like Andhra Pradesh, Goa, Haryana, Kerala, Karnataka, Puducherry, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Telangana, Goa, Madhya Pradesh, etc. are few States where the scholarships are being utilised fully. There are few states like Bihar, Jharkhand, Mizoram, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, etc. and ICSE where the Scheme has not been utilised and is yet to meet the target of utilisation of the available quota. It can also be seen that students from some of the States/UTs like Meghalaya, Mizoram, Puducherry and Himachal Pradesh have not sent any application in the year 2015-16.

Allocation of Resources

The State-wise details about the money spent on the scheme every year. In the year 2013 (for three months), approximately Rs. 39.89 crore was spent under the scheme. In the financial year 2013-14, the Government spent approximately Rs. 71.82 crore. This expenditure further increased in the years 2014-15, 2015-16 and 2016-17 to Rs.146.37 crore, Rs. 144.57 crore and Rs. 101.18 crore respectively. For the initial three years, no money was spent in Bihar. Further, in Meghalaya and Mizoram, no money was spent in the last two years. States like West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, etc. are some of the states where more money was spent in the last five years than any other states in the country, due to the size of the 18-25

years age-group population (more quotas). As a result, they may be implementing the scheme more effectively than other states.

Empirical Evidence from the Field

The survey reveals that 91.70 per cent students informed that this scholarship scheme is a good scheme and should be continued in future. The information regarding difficulties faced at the time of applying for the session 2013-14, the survey revealed that the highest 21.2 per cent did not face any difficulty, 12.1 per cent responded about portal session problems and 8.3 per cent cited less awareness as a reason. But, those who faced problems mentioned that their college is not recognised by the Central Government and the website has various issues that led to pathetic problems. Further, there is hardly any awareness about the scheme so no information is easy to get and, as such, the related work gets delayed. During the offline process, standing in queue is a mammoth task, documentation attestation and affidavit work is very hectic. There are no self-explanatory guidelines regarding this scheme.

Similarly, in 2014-15, apart from the above problems, additional problems were faced by the students such as getting income certificate from the Tehsildaar's office which is not an easy task and sometime they do not issue. The website is not clear to explain and, in other words, it is not user- friendly. There is no one to help about the doubts related to the scheme. Some students applied, their applications have been accepted too, but they did not receive any money. The information on whether the application is accepted or rejected by the department concerned is not available. It is also mentioned by the students that the required information for the scholarship is missing from the college. The applying time is very short and many students have to travel to distant places to apply for the scholarship as they do not have facilities at their place. Further, in 2016-17, there are different issues faced by the students: website page is not available, online process is difficult, no proper information provided, generation of OTP, time stated was not certain/delay, travelling and other issues, no possibility of re-correction, spent their money and valuable time, option to edit even before the last date, they do not get fellowship, too many procedures to apply, results are declared late/check status, no proper messages are sent to the students regarding the scholarship.

Utilisation of scholarship amount by the beneficiaries

There are different modes of spending scholarship amounts by the students. There are five primary modes: buy books/stationery/hostel fee, family expenses, shopping, savings and others (give to siblings, college fee and daily traveller). In response, the highest 42.3 per cent students comprising 21.1 per cent males and 21.2 per cent females bought books/stationery/paid hostel fee, followed by savings (22.6 per cent students - 5.6 per cent males and 17 per cent females), followed by family expenses (15.6 per cent students - 5.5 per cent males and 10.1 per cent females). A total of 11.1 per cent students comprising 4.4 per cent males and 6.8 per cent females did not mention this response. Of the total respondents, there are 38.9 per cent males and 61.1 per cent females.

Impact of the scheme

The highest 61.1 per cent students comprising 23 per cent males and 38.1 per cent females revealed that they are moderately satisfied with the Scheme, 26.3 per cent students comprising 9.9 per cent males and 16.5 per cent females were fully satisfied, 7 per cent students comprising 3.0 per cent males and 4.0 per cent females were not satisfied. A total of 4.9 per cent students comprising 2.7 per cent males and 2.2 per cent females did not respond to this query. Of the total respondents, 38.9 per cent were males and 61.1 per cent females.

Findings

It was observed that the students, rather than gender, which are academically sound and economically deprived, should be given preference for the scholarship. The stream-wise ratio allotted in the Scheme is very unequal and a major block in the implementation. The scholarship should be distributed among the students without any stream/course difference. Therefore, equal importance should be given to all the courses and all the students in order to make the Scheme inclusive.

It was found that the amount under the Scheme is very low, especially for the students who have opted for Science stream in the colleges/universities. Moreover, students studying in National Institutes of Technology and Indian Institutes of Technology are paying a huge amount in fees; they cannot meet their educational needs with this marginal amount. Therefore, it was unanimously suggested by all the stakeholders that the amount should be increased from Rs.20000/- to Rs.40000/- per annum according to the courses. There

should be provision that students, if they so desire, may also avail of any other scholarship in addition to this one.

This scholarship has moderately supported the parents for fee. Due to this support, many poor students have got success to complete their higher studies. Many students who have been awarded the scholarship could not receive the scholarship amount into their account so far. The state level officers mentioned that the delay in the payment of scholarship amount is due to the central agencies. The institutions are not easily doing the verification of the students. There is no standard time-frame for the disbursal of the scholarship amount. The delay in the process is also increasing the distance between institutions and the students. The duration of each course is different and results of each course are announced at different times, due to which students are not able to verify their documents.

Some of the students have experienced that since the annual parental income ceiling high, there is a need to reduce it so that more and more poor students may get the proper benefit of the Scheme. If the income criterion is fixed from Rs.1 to 3 lakh, it will bring more benefits to the students. Many students have difficulties in getting income certificate and attestation/verification of ration card. Many of them were not able to get the income certificate from the respective authority. After getting the required documents, it is not clear to students whether these documents should be posted to Delhi or not.

The online system is not working properly. On many occasions, the web server is not available or working for applying or filling the forms. An OTP is required to register for applying the Scheme. Many students do not have mobiles and the mobile number which was given at the time of registration belongs to someone else and at the time of renewal, students do not have that particular number. Once wrong information is uploaded then it cannot be changed. Frequent changes in the software create confusion among the students and officials and not proper training provided for using the software. There are different 'user-ids' and 'passwords' for colleges so it also creates a problem in operations; therefore, there should be only one 'user-id' and 'password' for each college. Due to these online issues, the full quota is not being availed of in the state out of the total available quota.

Renewal of the scholarship is one of major issues in the process as the concerned guidelines are not clear. The students, at the time of renewal, face various problems both at the verification and banking levels. Late declaration of the results puts the renewals on hold. It is also found that low percentage in the first year is the major problem for non-renewal of the scholarship scheme. The renewal of scholarship may be done in a simple manner if the central agency releases funds to the students in time and the institutions concerned also co-operate with the students during verification of the students' applications.

This is one of the Schemes, beneficial for the general/open category students to continue their education; therefore, there is a need to promote the same and also increase the number of seats. This scholarship not only helped the students academically but also helped them in saving money for some emergency. There is a need to increase number of scholarships (quota) as there are a number of reservations/quotas by the age-group populations, gender, and caste. Since small states get very few scholarships, as a result, they are not taking much interest to implement the Scheme.

Conclusion

The paper identifies the fact that the new approach of the state to garner full participation among the people groups to represent in higher education by attaining the targets set by our country for participation in higher education. This requires significant increases in participation by under-represented groups. While there have been very welcome improvements in participation, there are still some substantial challenges to be faced by the state. The key challenge would now be to develop integrated approaches to underperformance in higher education.

Educational disadvantage in some areas is complex and multi-faceted and the policy is to be designed accordingly for getting proper responses. Obviously, it has been observed that no agency or institution can work alone to achieve quality and equity of access to higher education of the students/citizens. The higher education system is to be prioritised by the state and that will be to enhance co-operation across government departments, relevant agencies and all levels of education in order to achieve a more accessible and flexible higher education system.

Higher education will become even more diverse in the future through the establishment of new higher education providers and the creation of various consortia and partnerships between universities for research and/or teaching purposes to benefit tens of thousands of students. The higher education policy of a nation must have proliferative principles of

inclusiveness among teachers, scholars and research scientists from different universities and Institutes, with in-depth knowledge and understanding of their concerned subjects, generate new knowledge by publishing commendable books and articles, produce outstanding students, contribute immensely for the growth of a nation and to make an egalitarian society.

The study demonstrates that most socio-economic groups have been benefitting from the general expansion of higher-education opportunities but inequalities still persist. The traditional target groups of semi-skilled and unskilled manual workers remain significantly below national averages and the non-manual group currently derives least benefit from higher education.

Even though the incentive/scholarship programmes is a heart-warming for the students who have been studying in colleges and universities, the process of implementation of the scholarship seemed to be mind-boggling. The scheme also brings some impediments often in the process of sanctioning and disbursement as the amount given is delayed. The underprivileged sections of our society, which have been passing through under tremendous implications of inability and infringements to send their students to colleges will get a boost up through these scholarships and also their children will be benefitted by getting quality higher education, so that it will make a new history in the annals of Indian higher education. The scheme has provided opportunity to several poor and meritorious students from different social categories to continue their higher studies which were not possible without these scholarships. The scheme is indirectly helping to improve the quality, equity and excellence in higher education institutions.

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